

Original Article

Optimization of Printability Parameters of Chitosan Ink for Microextrusion-based 3D Bioprinting

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Chitosan as a 3D printing material has been explored extensively. The viscosity of the lower concentration of the material is unsuitable for microextrusion-based 3D printing, whereas higher concentrations are associated with needle clogging and high extrusion pressure requirements, limiting its application for tissue engineering and high-resolution printing. We prepared the low concentration chitosan ink and gelled it using heat treatment to optimize the printing parameters. This study aims to optimize printability parameters for microextrusion-based 3D printing using heat-treated chitosan ink dissolved in an alkali solvent. Various concentrations of heated chitosan ink (1-4%) were prepared and analyzed for their rheological and mechanical properties. The ink exhibited shear thinning behavior, crucial for extrusion-based printing. Rheological analysis indicated that higher concentrations (2.5% and 3%) had viscosities suitable for filament formation. Mechanical characterization demonstrated that higher chitosan concentrations provided better compressive strength, with 4% chitosan exhibiting the highest strength. The study also optimized printing parameters such as extrusion pressure, layer height, and print speed. Emphasizing the importance of ink concentration and extrusion parameters, the study found that 4% chitosan ink at 35°C is optimal for maintaining structural integrity in 3D printed constructs. These findings underscore the necessity of optimizing ink concentration and printing parameters to achieve high-quality 3D printed constructs suitable for biomedical applications.

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Introduction

Three-dimensional (3D) printing is a type of additive manufacturing (AM) that is used to create 3D objects layer-by-layer according to predefined digital blueprints [1]. In 1988, Klebe first demonstrated 3D printing, referring to the technique as ‘cytoscribing,’ which involved the precise placement of cells on a 2D substrate by employing a computer-controlled inkjet printer or graphics plotter [2]. In the field of biomedicine, 3D printing encompasses various additive manufacturing techniques that enable the precise placement of both materials and living cells to build three-dimensional biological constructs [2]. The printing materials used for such applications are called “inks”. The primary biofabrication methods used for handling inks include inkjet printing, laser-induced forward transfer, and extrusion-based printing [3]. Among these fabrication methods, extrusion-based 3D printing (also known as nozzle-based 3D printing) is especially

favoured by ink developers due to its versatility, ability to handle a wide range of ink viscosities, and is well-suited for printing at clinically relevant speeds [3]. Extrusion-based printing is a technique adapted from traditional thermoplastic 3D printing, which utilizes pneumatic or mechanical force (via air pressure or a screw) to drive the printing material through the nozzle onto a platform [4].

Cell viability and geometric precision are essential aspects of 3D printing. Both are influenced by printing parameters and the properties of the biomaterial [4]. There is always a trade-off between cell viability and printability. Applicability of the 3D printed construct is governed by cell viability, whereas printability is crucial for geometrical accuracy. Printability for ink is defined as the ease with which a structure can be printed with good resolution and maintain its structure after printing [5]. The printability of ink can usually be measured by the shape fidelity, resolution, and dimensional accuracy of the printed structures.

Printing parameters include a range of adjustable variables that impact the outcome of the printing process. These parameters are divided into two categories: process parameters, such as nozzle height, nozzle diameter, printing speed, and extrusion speed, which

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are controlled by the 3D printer; and material parameters, which pertain to the material's properties like composition, viscosity, and viscoelasticity [6]. Furthermore, these parameters affect cell viability by altering the shear forces within the ink during printing. A larger nozzle diameter reduces shear stress and minimizes cell damage, though it results in lower resolution. Similarly, increasing dispensing pressure also increases the shear stress and has been shown to significantly harm cell viability [3-7]. The term 'path height' refers to the vertical distance between the print bed and the printing nozzle. The extent of material spreading during printing is influenced by the chosen path height. Nozzle diameter affects the resolution by determining the filament diameter. As the complexity of the target print structure increases, support structures are required to prevent the collapse of the structure during printing. Appropriate patterns and materials must be selected. Higher viscosity hydrogels should be utilized as structural components. In this work, we have demonstrated the printability of chitosan ink for microextrusion-based 3D printing. It starts with the selection of a material concentration and the gelation of ink to improve the filament uniformity factor, followed by its extrudability analysis and print optimization to achieve a 3D printed structure.

Materials and Methods

Potassium hydroxide, urea, and lithium hydroxide (LOBA Chemi), Gelatin Type A bloom strength 300 (Sigma Aldrich), Shrimp shell chitosan ($\geq 75\%$ deacetylated, Himedia).

Chitosan ink preparation

Different concentration of chitosan (1-4%) was mixed in a solvent composed of 8 wt% urea/7 wt% KOH/4.5 wt% LiOH/in 80.5 wt% distilled water and frozen for 3 h at -30°C , then thawed at 25°C to mix extensively, and centrifuged at 4°C for 10 minutes at 7000 rpm to remove air bubbles. The prepared chitosan ink was ready to use for extrusion 3D printing. The ink was stored at 4°C before usage. Water (60°C) was used to crosslink the alkali-dissolved chitosan ink.

Viscosity and rheological analysis

Ink concentrations, i.e., 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, and 3%, were prepared for the rheological analysis. The study was performed on a Brookfield LV DV Next rheometer having a torque constant of 0.0673 mNm with a cone and plate setup using spindle CP-52 and a 0.005-inch (0.013 mm) gap between the sample cup and the spindle. The test parameters were 20°C in rotational mode. The rotational shear viscosity profile was analyzed between 0.1-300 s^{-1} shear rates. The viscosity vs. shear stress rheology was plotted. The power law equation was fitted according to the given formula, where γ is the shear rate, n , and K are the shear thinning coefficients, and η is the viscosity.

$$\eta = K\gamma^{(n-1)} \quad (1)$$

Mechanical characterization

Mechanical characterization of chitosan was performed using the TA3/100 probe for the compression test of the Brookfield CTC Texture Analyzer. Cylindrical constructs (35 x 9 mm) of 3% (35°C and 40°C) and 4% 35°C gelled chitosan were prepared. Compression testing parameters were as follows: load cell of 10000 g and target deformation of 50%. The test was performed at a speed of 1 mm/sec. The comparative evaluation of the effective elastic modulus, ultimate compressive strength of all the concentrations of chitosan, and different crosslinking temperatures has been performed to understand the effect of concentration and crosslinking temperature on the mechanical strength of the mold

and 3D printed construct.

Print optimization

The extrusion-based 3D printing largely depends on extrusion optimization. The extrusion test was performed manually for all the prepared concentrations using a pipette. Then, the concentrations that formed filaments were tested for extrusion using Allevi 2 (3D system, USA) 3D bioprinter. A 20-G blunt end needle was used to evaluate the extrusion of the chitosan inks. The .stl files of a 10 mm^3 hollow cube were used for the test. G-code was generated, and printing parameters were set to start the 3D printing. Print pressure, layer height, print speed, and needle diameters were the four parameters optimized.

Uniformity factor (U) and integrity factor (I)

The printability of the filament was evaluated after the optimization of the printing parameters. A single layer of a square and a circle of 10 mm^2 were 3D printed. Images were captured using a Nikon Ti microscope. The uniformity factor (U) was calculated according to the given equation.

$$U = L/L_t \quad (2)$$

where L is the actual horizontal length of the printed filament, and L_t is the theoretical length. The integrity factor (I) is defined as the ratio of the thickness of the 3D printed structure to the thickness of the 3D model.

Results and Discussion

Rheological characterization

Extrusion-based 3D printing was used in this current work, in which the material is extruded via shear force exerted by the compressed air, piston, or screw. When the material exhibits thinning behavior under the effect of shear force, it is called a shear thinning material. The material is essentially required to be shear thinning to be used in extrusion-based 3D printing. The shear-associated properties of the ink material were analyzed. Most of the natural polymers exhibit a non-Newtonian pseudo-plastic nature [8]. Figures 1A and 1B are the images of less viscous and viscous chitosan inks, respectively. Figure 1C shows the effect of an increase in shear stress on the viscosity. The viscosity decreased with increased shear stress, confirming the shear thinning leading to the flow initiation of the ink. The stress at flow initiation is called yield stress. The curve indicated the flowing behavior of the ink from the beginning of the increase of shear stress, as no steep drop in viscosity was noticed [9]. Therefore, the viscosity-shear stress graph suggested that the flow initiation of 2.5% and 3% ink was at 1.75 ± 0.08 Pa and 2.98 ± 0.14 Pa, respectively. This justifies the low yield stress of both ink concentrations. The yield stress increases as we increase the chitosan concentration in the ink. It was observed that inks with concentrations of 1%, 1.5%, and 2% exhibited viscosities of less than 50 poise, while 2.5% and 3% ink showed viscosities noticeably higher or close to 50 poise. Further, we performed a drop test. Upon extruding from the pipette, low viscosity inks, which have a viscosity of less than 50 poise, exhibited liquid-like properties and did not form filaments, whereas inks with a viscosity greater than 50 poise were able to form filamentous structures [10]. Therefore, low viscosity inks (1%, 1.5%, and 2%) were not considered further for analysis. To quantify the shear thinning behavior, a mathematical model named the Power law (equation 1) was fitted to the viscosity-shear rate plot. Power law fitted to filament-like 2.5 and 3% chitosan ink material gives the flow index $n = 0.93 \pm 0.02$, 0.87 ± 0.07 , and consistency index $K = 40.55 \pm 1.17$, 89.9 ± 4.11 , respectively. Pseudo-plastic materials

Figures 1: A) and B) show the less viscous chitosan (1%) and filament-like chitosan (3%), respectively. C) Shows the viscosity-shear stress curve of different concentrations of chitosan ink. D) Shows the shear stress-shear rate curve of different concentrations of chitosan ink

have a flow index value of less than 1. The extrudability of the ink materials improves with the lower consistency index [11-13] which can be interpreted as the requirement of low shear stress (pressure in our case) to initiate the extrusion [14]. The consistency index value of 1 and 1.5% chitosan was very low, describing its very high extrudability, which is not desirable for 3D printing applications as they do not retain the filament shape after extrusion (figure 1A). Figure 1D describes a non-linear relation between shear stress and the shear rate with a slight deviation from the linear proportionality, indicating the shear rate-dependent viscosity of ink. This is a characteristic feature of pseudo-plastic material.

Mechanical characterization

Mechanical characterization of the ink material is a crucial aspect of 3D printing. As the 3D printed structures are supposed to be used for biomedical applications, their mechanical properties should fall under the range of human tissues, which varies from 0.1 KPa to 1 MPa depending upon the location and type [15-19]. Here, we demonstrated the range of compressive strength obtained with different ink concentrations and gelation temperatures. The gelation depends on the concentration of the ink and the temperature of

the gelation. As shown in Figure 2A, a chitosan concentration of 4% with gelation at 35°C requires nearly 20 kPa stress to obtain 50% of the deformation, whereas 3% chitosan ink with gelation at 35°C requires less than 2 kPa stress for 50% deformation. The structures noticeably regained their original shape when the compressive stress was removed. Figure 2B describes the role of chitosan concentration and gelation temperature on the compressive strength of chitosan ink. Compressive modulus of 4% with gelation at 35°C was found to be the highest, with 54.51 kPa, while 3% chitosan ink with gelation at 35°C showed 2.75 kPa.

Print optimization

Filament test

As mentioned above, the high viscous inks, including 2.5, 3, and 4%, were used for further analysis. Heat-induced gelation occurs in the chitosan ink dissolved in an alkali solvent [20]. In this test, the highly viscous inks were heated at two different temperatures (35°C and 40°C) for 30 minutes with continuous mixing to induce gelation; mixing was performed to induce uniform gelation. Chitosan concentrations of 2.5% did not show uniform gelation.

Figure 2: A) Shows the compressive stress-strain curve of 3% and 4% chitosan ink with gelation at different temperatures. B) Shows compressive modulus of 3% and 4% chitosan ink with gelation at different temperatures

After gelation, the inks were filled into syringes for manual extrusion. On manual extrusion, ink concentrations of 3 and 4% showed filament formation (figure 3). Then, we tested the layer stacking by simply manually extruding two layers of a 10 mm² square. During manual extrusion, 3% ink at 35°C, 3% at 40°C, and 4% at 35°C showed uniform filament formation and layer stacking. However, nonuniform extrusion was observed with 4% ink gelled at 40°C, possibly due to over-gelation at high chitosan concentration and gelation temperature (figure 3D). All three concentrations retained their structure and size. Following the nonuniformity in extrusion of 4% at 40°C chitosan ink, we only carried out the work with 3% at 35°C, 3% at 40°C, and 4% at 35°C chitosan inks. Figure

4 shows the images of printed structures using 3% at 35°C, 3% at 40°C, and 4% at 35°C chitosan inks. The role of gelation of ink prior to the printing ensured filament stability with lower concentrations of the chitosan ink. It is not required to use a higher concentration of chitosan, which saves the amount of material used and requires less extrusion pressure. It is often not possible to use high gauge size needles for high-viscosity material, limiting the resolution of the printed structures. Whereas when we use a lower concentration of material, a high gauge needle can be used to print high-resolution structures.

Extrusion Pressure

After manual extrusion, further evaluation of the 3% inks at 35°C and 40°C, as well as the 4% ink at 35°C, was conducted using 3D printing. 3% and 4% chitosan inks were filled in a syringe fitted with a 20G printing needle and extruded to optimize the extrusion pressure for 3D printing. The printing was optimized using Allevi 2 (3D system, USA) an extrusion-based 3D bioprinter. Extrusion pressure is the first printing parameter required to be optimized for printing. The extrusion of a material depends on viscosity, print temperature, and needle diameter used during printing. The pressure at which the material starts to extrude is called extrusion pressure, but this pressure may not be sufficient to extrude a continuous filament with the movement of the needle during printing. Therefore, a higher pressure was required to obtain a continuous filament during the printing process. To achieve a continuous print filament, we printed a single-layer square of 10 mm² at different pressures. It was observed that the 4% ink at 35°C showed uniform printing, layer stacking, and structure retention. While the 3% inks at 35°C and 40°C were printable and formed filaments, they started spreading, resulting in the broadening of the filaments after extrusion. The role of extrusion pressure is described in figure 5.

Layer height

It is defined as the height at which the second filament will be deposited. If the layer height is very low, then the needle will scratch the previously printed layer, causing the broadening of the first layer, increasing the horizontal dimension, and decreasing the vertical dimension of the 3D printed structures (Figure 5 E and F). Extra material will be accumulated on the edges of the structures. A layer

Figure 3: A, B, C, and D are the images of the manual extrusion of the 3 and 4% chitosan inks heated at 35°C and 40°C. Scale bar 10 mm

Figure 4: A and B are the images of 3D printed square structures (10 mm²) using 3% chitosan with gelation at 35°C and 40°C, respectively. C is the image of a 3D printed square structure (10 mm²) using 4% chitosan with gelation at 35°C. Scale bar 10 mm

height greater than the diameter of the needle will prevent the proper stacking of the upcoming layer to the previous layers, dislocating the filament deposition and causing complete disturbance in printing. This criterion is often challenged in extrusion 3D printing as the extruded material exhibits the die-swelling effect. The extruded filament diameter increases as it comes out of the needle. This causes the larger diameter of the extruded filament than the actual needle diameter [21]. An optimized layer height of 0.5 mm was used in the study. An optimized layer height of 0.5 mm was used in the study. However, a 3D printed structure using a layer height of 0.2 mm is shown in Figure 5E, whereas Figure 5F shows the image of a 3D printed structure using a layer height of 0.5 mm, having sharp edges and thin walls as compared to a

structure printed with a 0.2 mm layer height at the same print pressure. The role of layer height optimization is more significant in two-material extrusion 3D printing. Moreover, the uniformity factor describes the accuracy of the 3D-printed structure. For a uniform strand $U=1$ and a nonuniform $U>1$. The uniformity factor was found to be slightly greater than 1. The integrity factor (I) is defined as the ratio of the thickness of the 3D printed structure to the thickness of the 3D model [22]. The structures showed an integrity factor of 1.5. The print speed also plays a role in determining the integrity of the 3D-printed structures. The material extrusion at a particular pressure varies with print speed. The higher the print speed, the lower the material extrusion. A second challenge is the retraction of the material. The material was retracted when the extruder moved to print the next layer; a defect was observed at high speed when the extrusion lagged the print speed, causing empty spots at the corner of each layer. Table 1 describes the optimized values of 3D printing parameters for the given formulations of printable ink.

Figure 5: A and B are images of a 3D printed square structures (10 mm²) using chitosan ink with 35 and 40 psi pressure, respectively. C and D are the images of a single filament of chitosan ink printed at 35 and 40 psi pressure. E and F are images of a 3D printed square structures (10 mm²) using chitosan ink with layer heights of 0.2 and 0.5 mm, respectively. Scale bar, A, B, E, and F 10 mm, C and D 50 μ m

Conclusion

This study successfully demonstrates the optimization of printability parameters for microextrusion-based 3D printing using chitosan ink, highlighting significant insights into the material's rheological and mechanical properties. The research shows that chitosan, a biopolymer derived from shrimp shells, exhibits shear

Table 1: Optimized values of 3D printing parameters for the given formulations of printable ink

Parameters Optimized	Values
Concentration	4% chitosan with gelation at 35°C
Temperature	25°C
Printing speed	6 mm/sec
Nozzle diameter	20G
Needle inner diameter	0.26 mm
Extrusion pressure	40
Fill density	Null
Layer height	0.5 mm
Print file	10 mm ² square

thinning behavior, which is crucial for extrusion-based printing. Rheological analyses indicate that chitosan concentrations of 2.5% and 3% possess viscosities conducive to filament formation, essential for maintaining structural integrity during and after the printing process. Mechanical characterization further reveals that higher chitosan concentrations, particularly 4%, enhance the compressive strength of the printed constructs, rendering them more suitable for biomedical applications where mechanical resilience is critical. The study's findings underscore the importance of optimizing both the ink concentration and the printing parameters to achieve high-quality, structurally sound 3D printed constructs. The study meticulously optimized key printing parameters, including extrusion pressure, layer height, and print speed. This optimization process was critical to ensuring the printability and fidelity of the constructs, which were validated through various mechanical and rheological tests. The optimal conditions identified were a 4% chitosan ink concentration extruded at 35°C, which provided the best balance between printability and mechanical strength.

This research emphasizes the significant role of material properties in the 3D printing process. The study paves the way for future applications of chitosan-based inks in tissue engineering and other biomedical fields by identifying and optimizing the ideal concentrations and extrusion parameters. The comprehensive analysis provided in this study offers valuable insights into the behavior of chitosan inks under different conditions, contributing to the broader understanding and advancement of 3D printing technologies.

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